

Hybrid Flapping and Gliding Flight for Robot Bird using Closed-Loop Nonlinear Optimal Control: Indoors Experimentation

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Abstract—Hybrid flight of flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) is one of the advantages of flapping-wing mechanisms for thrust and lift generation of aerial platforms. Hybrid flight refers to the capacity of switching between flapping and gliding modes. The source of thrust and lift generation is the flapping state; however, in the condition of favorable wind and sufficient height from the ground, gliding flight can be achieved. The gliding phase, flight without a main flapping motor offers several important features: requiring less energy per covered horizontal distance, and flight without oscillation. The focus of this work is to investigate the reduction of oscillation in indoor flights where the flight zone is a closed limited space. In point-to-point control of the robot bird, the last meter approach to the final desired point, ideally demands less oscillations. The implementation of the closed-loop nonlinear control on the FWFR is studied; the controller is so-called the state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE). The experiments showed successful switching between flapping and gliding controllers in the indoor tests. The lack of wind in an indoor environment increases the difficulty of gliding and the results showed a significant decrease in height with an increase in the gliding distance.

Keywords: FWFR; Flapping-wing; Aerial robotics; Nonlinear optimal control; SDRE; UAVs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Flapping-wing robots offer a safer flight close to people/nature since they do not need high-speed rotary propellers which is essential for unmanned multi-rotor aerial platforms. This point provoked recently a trend in research on bird-like robots [1]–[4]. One of the most important capabilities of flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) is switching between the flapping and gliding modes. This hybrid flight condition provides three advantages: energy saving while the bird flies in gliding mode [5], omitting the oscillations, and flight in the steady-state condition of flapping. The oscillations due to flapping cause inaccuracy in position control for applications such as perching [6], position control [7], etc. Zufferey et al. performed flight control and perching on a rigid branch in an indoor testbed [6]. An active leg-claw system was designed to compensate for the oscillations of the FWFR in the last meter approaching phase to the branch location. The amplitude of the oscillations was between 10 to 15(cm) [8]. Switching to gliding mode will omit the oscillations caused by flapping and might be helpful for position control. However, the limited flight zone (15(m) diagonal space in indoor testbed)

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Fig. 1. The FWFR prototype for indoor flights. The lightweight updated design 575(g) for hybrid flight.

and lack of favorable wind impose some challenges in the gliding time and limit that. Here in this work, the topic of hybrid flapping and gliding will be investigated using a nonlinear optimal control method.

The control of the FWFR is a critical part of a successful flight from the initial to final condition. The linear control design was implemented on the FWFR prototypes many times. Chand et al. used an intelligent proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller for the flapping wing robot, SlowHawk2 [9]. The motivation for using linear non-model-based control was to avoid the complexity of the dynamics and unknown aerodynamics terms of the FWFR. The proportional-derivative (PD) control was used for a hummingbird-like flapping wing robot [10]. The objective was to control a lightweight 21(g) platform for stable hovering. Zhong et al. employed PID control for flapping wing platforms to obtain autonomous flight conditions for the robot bird [11]. The controllers such as optimal, nonlinear, fuzzy approach, etc. were exercised on FWFR to increase the performance, surveyed briefly in the following.

A combination of linear PID controllers was designed for a large FWFR with a fuzzy controller to change the mode between the rules and conditions [12]. Flight tests were performed outdoors for trajectory tracking of a circular path of 30(m) radius. Biswal et al. designed a linear quadratic regulator (LQR) control for a micro flapping wing aerial system [13]. Nonlinear parameter optimization was done to estimate the linearized dynamics and to design a set

of LQR controllers for the system. He et al. designed and implemented an adaptive control on the dynamic model of a flapping-wing robot [14]. Optimal model-based/model-free control was implemented on flapping systems [15]. The mentioned implemented methods were non-model-based; they used optimization or estimation to find suitable parameters and fit the models.

The dynamics of the FWFR are more complex than the fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [16]–[21]. Orłowski and Girard studied the multi-body dynamics of a flapping wing robot, focusing on upstroke and downstroke aerodynamics terms of the flapping [22]. Tsuchiya et al. designed and built a testbed for experimentation and analyzing the lift power of a tailless flapping wing system [23]. Fluid interaction in the structure and dynamics of the flapping wing system was presented [24]. Complexity in the dynamics of flapping wing robots led to alternative modeling methods to apply nonlinear controllers for FWFR systems. The equivalent dynamics for FWFR were proposed to replicate the oscillation of flapping with a mass-spring-damper system in vertical dynamics [8]. The equivalent system generated the same periodic oscillations for the dynamics and was used in the proportional control implementation on the vertical dynamics for verification and comparison [25]. The extended version of equivalent dynamics for a six-degree-of-freedom (DoF) system was implemented using the state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) [7]. The regulation (point-to-point) control was done for an FWFR in an indoor testbed equipped with visual position feedback to the control unit.

The SDRE is one of the popular methods in the nonlinear optimal control domain for experimental implementations [26]–[32]. Korayem and Lademakhi applied the SDRE design for estimation and control simultaneously for flexible joint manipulators [33]. LabVIEW was used as an interface between the SDRE control loop in the main computer and the robot's processor. Arduino-MATLAB interface is also a highly reported method for stationary tests using the SDRE. An inverted pendulum was controlled using this approach [34], and a variable-pitch rotor-based pendulum [35]. Arican et al. designed and implemented the SDRE on an experimental test bench of a helicopter [36]. A regional pole assignment method was used to facilitate the tuning of the weighting matrices of the optimal control. For the onboard computations, the SDRE must be run on an independent platform, i.e. FWFR [7]. The lightweight processors for onboard computations, specifically for the FWFR are weaker than personal computers and laptops, hence, the implementation of nonlinear optimal controllers is challenging.

The main contribution of this work is to:

- C1. Design and implement a hybrid nonlinear optimal SDRE for flapping control, and gliding control using linear designs. The objective is to investigate hybrid flight in an indoor confined space. The SDRE control on an FWFR was reported (only flapping in the entire flight zone) [7], which motivated this current work to apply a hybrid design for flapping/gliding.
- C2. Hybrid flapping and gliding outdoor was presented

Fig. 2. The model and schematic of the FWFR; axis and variables definition for the model [7].

using linear controllers, i.e. [37]; this current work presents closed-loop nonlinear optimal flight control within $\approx 15(\text{m})$ indoor space.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents a brief formulation of the dynamics of the FWFR. The control structure including flapping, gliding, and switching are reported in Section III. Section IV expresses the setup details. The results are shown in Section V, and the summary of the work is presented in Section VI.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE FWFR: A BRIEF PRESENTATION

The equivalent dynamic model of an FWFR is an augmentation of a 3D rigid body and an equivalent eccentric periodic mass-spring-damper system. The generalized coordinates of the main body are set $\mathbf{q} = \{x_c, y_c, z_c, \phi, \theta, \psi\}$, where position vector of the center-of-mass (CoM) is $\xi_1 = [x_c, y_c, z_c]^T (\text{m})$, and the orientation vector is $\xi_2 = [\phi, \theta, \psi]^T (\text{rad})$, presented in Fig. 2. The kinematic of the robot is defined by $\dot{\xi}_1 = \mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2)\mathbf{v}_1$ and $\dot{\xi}_2 = \mathbf{T}(\xi_2)\mathbf{v}_2$ in which $\mathbf{v}_1 = [u, v, w]^T (\text{m/s})$ and $\mathbf{v}_2 = [p, q, r]^T (\text{rad/s})$ are linear and angular velocities of the FWFR, and details of $\mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2)$, $\mathbf{T}(\xi_2)$ matrices are referred to [7]. The state variables of the system are collected in the vector:

$$\mathbf{x} = [\xi_1^T, \xi_2^T, \mathbf{v}_1^T, \mathbf{v}_2^T]^T. \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) results in the state-space representation of the system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2)\mathbf{v}_1 \\ \mathbf{T}(\xi_2)\mathbf{v}_2 \\ \mathbf{R}_b^{-1}(\xi_2) \left(\frac{1}{m_b} \mathbf{R}_b(\xi_2) \mathbf{E}_w(z_c, z_w) - m_b g \mathbf{e}_3 - \underbrace{\dot{\mathbf{R}}_b(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_1}_{\approx 0} \right) \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2) \left(-\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2) \mathbf{c}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2) - \underbrace{\dot{\mathbf{T}}(\xi_2) \mathbf{v}_2}_{\approx 0} \right) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{1}{m_b} \mathbf{F}_B \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2) \mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2) \boldsymbol{\tau}_B \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. The block diagram of the FWFR's control architecture.

where $g(\text{m/s}^2)$ is gravity constant, $m_b(\text{kg})$ is mass of the body of the base, $\mathbf{J}(\xi_2) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix of orientation dynamic, $\mathbf{c}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2) : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ collects the Coriolis and centrifugal terms, $\mathbf{F}_B \in \mathbb{R}^3(\text{N})$ is the applied force vector, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_B \in \mathbb{R}^3(\text{Nm})$ is the input torque vector. The generalized coordinate of the vertical motion of the eccentric oscillatory mass of wings is $z_w = z_0 \sin \omega t$ in which $z_0(\text{m})$ is the amplitude and $\omega \in \mathbb{R}(\text{rad/s})$ is the frequency of the oscillations. The interaction of the equivalent vertical dynamic of the wing is arranged in a vector:

$$\mathbf{E}_w(z_c, z_w) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ m_w \ddot{z}_w + c \dot{z}_w + k z_w - c \dot{z}_c - k z_c \end{bmatrix}$$

where $m_w(\text{kg})$ is mass of the wings, $k(\text{N/m})$ is the elastic constant, and $c(\text{Ns/m})$ is the damping coefficient. The control design for the model of the system, Eq. (2), is presented in Section III.

III. CONTROL DESIGN

A. Flapping

1) *Orientation*: The orientation dynamic of the FWFR is controlled using the SDRE. The SDRE is applied to nonlinear systems in the form of:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u}, \quad (3)$$

where the states are defined in vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and the inputs in vector $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization matrices.

The cost function of optimal control is:

$$J(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty [\mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{x}] dt, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ and $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are weighting matrices for inputs and states; both matrices are symmetric positive, $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x})$ is definite and $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x})$ is semi-definite.

The control law of the SDRE is [38]:

$$\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{x}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the sub-optimal gain. The control gain in (5) is the symmetric positive-definite solution to the SDRE:

$$\mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (6)$$

In order to solve the Riccati equation (6), the controllability and observability of the SDC parameterization must be met. The controllability condition is satisfied when the rank of the controllability matrix for the pair of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})\}$ is full [39]. The observability matrix for the pair $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x})\}$ must be full rank as well to guarantee observability condition [26]. $\mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x})$ is the Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x})$ in (4).

The nonlinear system, Eq. (3), for orientation part of (2) is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\xi}_2 \\ \dot{v}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{T}(\xi_2) \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2)\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2)\mathbf{C}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2)\mathbf{T}(\xi_2) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x})} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_2 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2)\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2) \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})} \boldsymbol{\tau}_B, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{c}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2) = \mathbf{C}(\xi_2, \dot{\xi}_2)\dot{\xi}_2$ is held.

Using the SDC (7) and weighting matrices with proper dimension, one could solve the SDRE (6) and use the input law (5) to close the control loop for the orientation dynamic. The control law (5) for the orientation dynamic, considering the regulation to a desired endpoint, is rewritten as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_B = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{e}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{e} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi - \phi_{\text{des}} \\ \theta - \theta_{\text{des}} \\ \psi - \psi_{\text{des}} \\ \dot{\phi} - \dot{\phi}_{\text{des}} \\ \dot{\theta} - \dot{\theta}_{\text{des}} \\ \dot{\psi} - \dot{\psi}_{\text{des}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The input law (8) is mapped to the angles of the rudder and elevators using a mixer matrix

$$\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{M}_x^{-1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_B,$$

Fig. 4. The experimental platform of the FWFR.

in which $\mathbf{M}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta} = [\delta_R, \delta_{ER}, \delta_{EL}]^T$ (rad) in which the components of $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ vector are angles of the rudder, right elevator, and left elevator. The controller regulates the system around the zero position of the rudder and elevators that provide the pulse-width-modulation (PWM) inputs:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left}} \end{bmatrix} = \text{int}(\boldsymbol{\delta}_B) + \begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left},0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where $\text{int}(\cdot)$ is an integer function that releases the integer value of its input, i.e. $\text{PWM}_{\text{rudder},0}$ is the PWM value that puts the servomotor in the correct zero position. Moreover, the upper and lower bounds of the PWM values will be applied through a set of constraints in the control code.

2) *Translation*: The robotic bird is an under-actuated system with four inputs: a flapping, and three motions of the tails. This provokes some flight assumptions for modeling and control such as the existence of sufficient forward velocity for the system to keep the stability of the motion. Therefore, the forward input control force for the translation dynamic is zero $F_x = 0$. In this specific flapping and gliding maneuver, the focus is not on Y -axis control, then we also neglect the lateral position control to simplify the implementation. This implies that the control in the X - and Y -axis are not in the interest of this work due to the limited confined space of the experimental flight zone and straight locomotion of the robot bird. For vertical dynamics of the translation part, PD control is used:

$$F_z = -\bar{K}_{P,z}e_z - \bar{K}_{D,z}\dot{e}_z, \quad (10)$$

in which $\bar{K}_{P,z}$ and $\bar{K}_{D,z}$ are proportional and derivative gains for height control, respectively; $e_z = z_c - z_{\text{des}}$ is vertical error of the robot bird in regulation control.

3) *FWFR Control*: The overall control of the FWFR is a combination of the translation and orientation for the four available actuators of the system. The control block diagram of the FWFR is illustrated in Fig. 3. Mapping the translation control law (10) and combining that with PWM inputs of the orientation control (9) generate the overall PWM input law

Fig. 5. The flight path and robot oscillations in flapping and gliding phase, point-to-point control. The flapping did not stop immediately when the motor turned off. The reason was that the position of the wing is not known when the robot stops the flapping motor and it might complete one cycle to reach the rest position. Designing a mechanism for locking the flapping at a specific point is proposed for future studies.

of the FWFR:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{int}(-K_{P,z}e_z - K_{D,z}\dot{e}_z) \\ \text{int}(\delta_R) \\ \text{int}(\delta_{ER}) \\ \text{int}(\delta_{EL}) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left},0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

in which i.e. $K_{P,z}$ is the mapped gain of $\bar{K}_{P,z}$.

B. Switching and Gliding

The switching command to change the control law from flapping to gliding is triggered by a position measurement on the X -axis value. The approximate diagonal flight path is 15(m). Selecting the center of the Opti-Track testbed as the location of the global reference frame, the limits in X -axis

are defined in the limit of $[-5.78, 8](\text{m})$. The switching point of flapping to gliding is selected $5.75(\text{m})$, where the control law of the total PWM inputs (11) is changed into:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator,right}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator,left}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \text{int}(\delta_R) \\ \text{int}(\Gamma_{\text{PD,ER}}) \\ \text{int}(\Gamma_{\text{PD,EL}}) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator,right},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator,left},0} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\text{int}(\cdot)$ is an integer function, and new elevator control input laws are:

$$\Gamma_{\text{PD,ER}} = -[-K_{\text{P},\phi}e_\phi - K_{\text{D},\phi}\dot{e}_\phi] + [-K_{\text{P},\theta}e_\theta - K_{\text{D},\theta}\dot{e}_\theta] - [-K_{\text{P},z}e_z - K_{\text{D},z}\dot{e}_z], \quad (12)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{PD,EL}} = -[-K_{\text{P},\phi}e_\phi - K_{\text{D},\phi}\dot{e}_\phi] - [-K_{\text{P},\theta}e_\theta - K_{\text{D},\theta}\dot{e}_\theta] + [-K_{\text{P},z}e_z - K_{\text{D},z}\dot{e}_z], \quad (13)$$

where i.e. $K_{\text{P},\phi}$ is the control gain of the roll control, $e_\theta = \theta - \theta_{\text{des}}$ is the error in pitch angle. In order to have control in the Z-axis after switching off the flapping motor, a PD control gain is added to the elevator actuators. Inside each bracket in the control laws (12) and (13) is a stable PD control, and different signs before the brackets are set based on the direction of the servomotor actuators.

Remark 1: It must be noticed that the height and pitch angle for the first phase of the flapping flight are different from the height and pitch angle of the final point at the end of the gliding. The height in the middle point (switching point) must be higher than the endpoint since in the gliding phase the bird loses height. The pitch angle of the final desired point at the end of the gliding point should be less than the pitch angle of the switching point to give the bird more gliding space. The reason is that a high-pitch angle acts like a brake in the flight of the FWFR.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The robot bird is a $575(\text{g})$ platform without the weight of the battery. The power supply is a four-cell Lipo type battery $14.8(\text{V})$ with $450(\text{mAh})$. The main flapping motor is a brushless DC Hacker A20-26M kv1130 that is connected to a reduction gears with a transmission ratio of 1:42. The platform and the components of the system are shown in Fig. 4. Three servomotors are designed for actuation of the tails (one rudder and two elevators), SH-0255MG type, working with $5(\text{V})$ voltage, provided by LM7805 regulator. The input PWM signals are computed in the main processor of the robot, Raspberry PI 3B+, and are generated by the PWM generator module PCA9685. To power the processor, an XL4015 regulator is used, set at $5.2(\text{V})$.

V. RESULTS

A launching system consisting of a linear motorized guideline is placed at the corner of the Opti-Track flight zone for the generation of the initial speed of flight for the robot bird. The launcher location defines the initial condition of generalized coordinates $\mathbf{q}(0) = \{-4.7, 3.66, 1.84, 0, -0.19, -0.56\}(\text{m}, \text{rad})$. The initial condition is found based on the position of the bird on the

Fig. 6. The position and orientation state variables of the FWFR.

launcher, reading the coordinates from the OptiTrack, the origin is the center of the flight area. The initial speed of the launcher is $\approx 4(\text{m/s})$ and reduces slightly after detachment. The expected flight trajectory is a diagonal line between two corners of the Opti-Track zone; hence, the final condition is set as $\mathbf{q}(t_f) = \{8, -3.5, z_{\text{des}}, 0, \theta_{\text{des}}, -0.3\}(\text{m}, \text{rad})$. The first set point of the height and pitch angle for the flapping flight is $z_{\text{des}} = 2.65(\text{m})$ and $\theta_{\text{des}} = -0.55(\text{rad})$ which is changed at $x_c = 5.75(\text{m})$.

At the switching point, the frequency of the flapping is set to zero, the new set-points of $z_{\text{des}} = 2(\text{m})$ and $\theta_{\text{des}} = 0.25(\text{rad})$ are applied. The inverse of the mixer matrix is defined as

$$\mathbf{M}_{\mathbf{x}}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 300 \\ -150 & 150 & 0 \\ -150 & -150 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The weighting matrices of states and inputs are set as $\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(1, 1, 1, 0.01, 0.01, 0.01)$ and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3}$, respectively. The control gain of flapping phase are tuned as $K_{\text{P},z} = 250$ and $K_{\text{D},z} = 3.5$. For the gliding phase, the control parameters are set as $K_{\text{P},\phi} = K_{\text{P},\theta} = 100$, $K_{\text{D},\phi} = K_{\text{D},\theta} = 1$, $K_{\text{P},z} = 5$ and $K_{\text{D},z} = 0.2$.

The results were obtained for the flight test during $5.15(\text{s})$ flapping and gliding. It consists of $4.5(\text{s})$ of flight for the flapping phase and $0.65(\text{s})$ for gliding. It indicates 87% flapping and 13% gliding. The robot increased height to $3.12(\text{m})$ due to overshoot and reached $2.42(\text{m})$ close to switching point with $23(\text{cm})$ error, Fig. 5. The final error of gliding was obtained $8.28(\text{cm})$, presented in Fig. 6-(c). The pitch angle is also regulated towards the desired one with $0.1(\text{rad})$ error, see Fig. 6-(e). The roll angle control made

Fig. 7. The velocity state variables of the FWFR.

the robot to move towards the final point, the other corner of the Opti-Track area, with an error less than 0.15(rad). The velocity states are illustrated in Fig. 7. The PWM inputs of the tails actuators and flapping motor are shown in Fig. 8. The flapping motor stopped at the switching point presented in Fig. 8-(a).

The expectation of the flapping and gliding in outdoor flight is keeping stability and height of the flight for several seconds and losing a little bit of height in case of favorable wind. This will depend on flight height as well. In indoor experimentation, there is no wind, and the height is less than 3(m). These conditions impose severe height loss when the FWFR switches to gliding, shown in Fig. 5. This short time and limited gliding phase make the application of hybrid flight more difficult for perching, control with high precision, etc. Increasing the gliding time also can be seen in Fig. 9 when it reached the height 1.35(m) with severe loss. It might be also observed that the flapping did not stop immediately when the motor turned off, Fig. 6-(c). The reason was that the position of the wing is not known when the robot stops the flapping motor and it might complete one cycle to reach the rest position. This is more clear when the gliding is longer, see Fig. 9. Designing a mechanism for locking the flapping at a specific point is proposed for future studies and more investigation on increasing the gliding flight in indoor space.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a study on a hybrid flight of a flapping wing robot bird in an indoor confined space. The Opti-Track flight zone of the laboratory offered us limited space for flight experiments of the FWFR. The hybrid flight offers several important benefits to motion control such as energy

Fig. 8. The inputs variables of the FWFR.

Fig. 9. The flight path and diving the robot.

saving when the flapping is off, and oscillation removal. In this work, the preliminary works to perform this switching in flapping and gliding were done using a combination of linear and nonlinear control. The flapping part (from the launching point to the first set point of the flight path) used the SDRE control for orientation control and PD for height control. The second gliding phase used linear controllers for the rest of the control actions, except for the flapping which was set to zero. The experiment showed acceptable preliminary results for performing hybrid indoor flights, the final error of gliding was obtained 8.28(cm). This topic needs more investigation to push it towards applications and error reduction in future studies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support from the Advanced Grant of the European Research Council GRIFFIN, Ac-

tion 788247, and the Hybrid AERial Aquatic robotic system for sampling, monitoring and intervention (HAERA, PID2020-119027RB-I00) funded by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovacion, and was supported by the R+D+i project TED2021-131716B-C22, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

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